

(8.05 g) in hot acetone (150 ml). The clear solution of brucine salt on two fractional crystallisations gave (-)-nitrile, m.p. 178°, $[\alpha]_D - 18^\circ$ (c=1.2) and (+)-nitrile, m.p. 176° $[\alpha]_D + 15^\circ$.

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Synthesis of Some 4-Hydroxybromoquinoline-3-Carboxylic Acids

N. C. MEHTA and C. M. DESAI

P. T. S. College of Science, Surat

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IN continuation of our previous work^{1,2} attempts were made to apply the acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid method to cyclise acrylates prepared by condensing ethyl ethoxymethylene-malonate or cyanoacetate with 5-bromo-*o*-toluidine, 3-bromo-*p*-toluidine, 4:6-dibromo-*m*-toluidine, 4-bromo-*o*-anisidine and 4-bromo-*o*-phenetidine. Since the yields of the cyclised products obtained with this method were poor due to the decomposition of the acrylates resulting in the formation of bromoacetylanilides, the acrylates were cyclised by the thermal method of Price and Roberts³.

TABLE-1

ARYLAMINOACRYLATES $R_1 = -COOC_2H_5$ OR $-CN$

	R_2	R_3	R_4	R_1	Yield %	m.p.s.	R_1'	Yield %	m.p.s
1.	H	Br	CH_3	$-COOC_2H_5$	77	106°	$-CN$	76	195°
2.	H	CH_3	Br	"	83	86	"	96	192
3.	CH_3	Br	Br	"	75	Sticky	"	51	225
4.	Br	H	OCH_3	"	34	118	"	31	140
5.	Br	H	OC_2H_5	"	93	105	"	37	173

TABLE-2

4-HYDROXYQUINOLINES

	R_2	R_3	R_4	(a) R_1	Yield %	m.p.s	(b) R_1	Yield %	m.p.s.	R_1	Yield: % a b	m.p.s.
1.	H	Br	CH_3	$-COOC_2H_5$	77	310	$-CN$	94	330° dec.	$-COOH$	78 41	301° dec.
2.	H	CH_3	Br	"	88	262	"	61	360	"	68 75	360
3.	CH_3	Br	Br	"	27	305	"	84	300 dec.	"	72 33	277
4.	Br	H	OCH_3	"	52	295	"	28	200	"	87 34	290
5.	Br	H	OC_2H_5	"	Sticky		"	19	291 dec.	"	19.5 56	281

Experimental

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonates & -cyanoacetates :

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonates were prepared by the method of Duffin and Kendall⁴ from the appropriate bromarylamine and ethyl ethoxymethylene-malonate by heating the mixture at 110° and the corresponding cyanoacetates by the method of Snyder and Jones⁵ by heating the mixture of the arylamine, ethyl cyanoacetate and ethyl orthoformate at 160-165° and the acrylates were purified by the usual treatment (details vide Table 1).

3-Carboethoxy- and 3-cyano-4-hydroxybromoquinolines :

Ethyl bromarylaminoethylene-malonate (15 g) or cyanoacetate (10 g) was cyclised to corresponding quinoline in boiling diphenyl ether (150 cc) and the product crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid (Table 2).

4-hydroxybromoquinoline-3-carboxylic acids :

3-Carboethoxyquinolines were hydrolysed by refluxing with 2N ethanolic sodium hydroxide for 3 hours and the 3-cyanoquinolines with an aqueous mixture of sulphuric and acetic acids (each 25 cc). Neutralisation of the basic or acidic solution gave the corresponding carboxylic acids (Table 2) which were purified by repeated alkali and acid treatment. The mixed m.p.s of corresponding acids in both cases did not show any depression.

Elemental analysis of (N) & (Br) were found to be within $\pm 4\%$ of the theoretical value for all the compounds prepared.

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Chromic Acid Oxidation of Some Substituted 2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl Alcohols

B. K. SARKHEL and J. N. SRIVASTAVA

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

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2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl alcohols have been shown¹⁻⁴ to be transformed into their corresponding isochroman-1-ones through the respective isochromans. Substituted 2-Hydroxymethylphenethyl alcohols(I) could now be directly oxidised to isochroman-1-ones(II) with chromic acid in one step following the procedure of Kubota *et al.*⁵. Also, IIf was converted to IIa by catalytic hydrogenation over Pd/C and subsequent treatment with diazomethane.

Ia, R = 4,5-di-OCH₃

Ib, R = 5,6-di-OCH₃

Ic, R = 4,6-di-OCH₃

Id, R = 4,5-O₂CH₃

Ie, R = 4-CH₃-6-OCH₃

If, R = 4-C₆H₅-CH₂O-5-OCH₃

IIa, R = 6,7-di-OCH₃

IIb, R = 5,6-di-OCH₃

IIc, R = 5,7-di-OCH₃

IId, R = 6,7-O₂CH₃

IIe, R = 5-OCH₃-7-CH₃

IIf, R = 6-OCH₃-7-C₆H₅-CH₂O

Experimental

6,7-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one : A solution of CrO₃ (0.3 g) in water (0.6 ml) and glacial AcOH (2 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to 2-hydroxymethyl-4,5-dimethoxyphenethyl alcohol (I; 0.2 g) dissolved in the same acid (6 ml). The temperature was maintained at 20-22° by occasional external cooling. After stirring for 0.5 hr. at the room temp., it was treated with an equal volume of water, extracted with CHCl₃ (2 × 25 ml), the extract washed with 2N Na₂CO₃, water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. A dark yellow solid left after solvent evaporation was dissolved in dry benzene. It was chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (30 g) and eluted with the same solvent. An almost colourless solid obtained was crystallised from ethylacetate-pet. ether (b.p. 60-80°) as colourless needles (0.07 g), m.p. 140-141°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample of the compound prepared earlier by a different route².

The following compounds were prepared by the method described above and crystallised from ethyl acetate-pet. ether unless otherwise mentioned.

5,6-Dimethoxyisochroman-1-one¹, m.p. 70-71° (37.5% yield) was purified by sublimation (bath temp. 90-95°/0.1 mm) followed by crystallisation from ethyl acetate.